

SIESTA Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

The objective of this Data Management Plan is to describe the research outputs reused and generated within the context of the EOSC-SIESTA project. It aims to detail the various characteristics that distinguish them and emphasize those aspects that facilitate the adoption of the FAIR principles.

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Secure Interactive
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Organizations

Radboud University, algoWatt SpA, ISI Foundation – Institute for Scientific Interchange, REGION HOVEDSTADEN, Institute of Physics of Cantabria (IFCA), Institut National de la Sante et de la Recherche Medicale (INSERM), Paris, France, CENDIO AKTIEBOLAG, INTERWAY, A.S., University of Leon, CNRS, Institute of Informatics - Slovak Academy of Sciences, DE LA CUEVA GONZALEZ COTERA JAVIER, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Madrid, Spain, National Statistics Institute (INE), Madrid, Spain

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: SIESTA Data Management Plan

Description:

The objective of this Data Management Plan is to describe the research outputs reused and generated within the context of the EOSC-SIESTA project. It aims to detail the various characteristics that distinguish them and emphasize those aspects that facilitate the adoption of the FAIR principles.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission|EC

Grants: Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics

Project: [Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

UC2.2: Medical Imaging [Input Dataset]

The input dataset contains structural T1-weighted MRI brain scans from 136 young individuals (87 females; age range from 18 to 35 years old) along with questionnaire-assessed measurements of trait-like chronotype, sleep quality and daytime sleepiness.

The analysis pipeline demonstrated here implements the MRIQC pipeline for obtaining standard quality control measures from an MRI dataset.

The data is organized according to the BIDS standard (combined size of 1.18GB) and mostly useful to scientists interested in circadian rhythmicity, structural brain correlates of chronotypes in humans and the effects of sleeping habits and latitude on brain anatomy.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

In WP15 we provide a number of concrete use cases for secure computing on medical imaging data. We will identify and prepare several representative datasets combined with several analysis pipelines, resulting in specific analysis outputs. The datasets selected for WP15 are all published and open access to allow all project partners to replicate and investigate all details for the use cases. However, the datasets are selected to represent similar EU datasets containing personal data that are the target for SIESTA.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

EOSC-SIESTA WP15 uses neuroimaging data that mainly classifies as primary data. The data has been curated and reformatted, but quality control may be limited and analysis outcomes are not part of the data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data is formatted according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. This relies on domain-specific formats for the individual files, including, but not limited to: JSON, TSV, NIFTI, EDF, BrainVision Core format, EEGLAB, Biosemi, OME-TIFF, ZARR.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.18GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information

- Other

We reuse existing data as there is no need to collect new data to demonstrate and identify medical neuroimaging pipelines' computational and interactive aspects. There is enough data available with the required characteristics, both open access and restricted access.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Michal Rafal Zareba and Magdalena Fafrowicz and Tadeusz Marek and Ewa Beldzik and Halszka Oginska and Aleksandra Domagalik (2022). Structural (t1) images of 136 young healthy adults; study of effects of chronotype, sleep quality and daytime sleepiness on brain structure. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds003826.v3.0.1

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Other

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/tree/main/usecase-2.2>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/Bids-standard/bids-schema>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Open Neuro supports API: <https://docs.openneuro.org/api.html>

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

OpenNeuro

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Structural (t1) images of 136 young healthy adults; study of effects of chronotype, sleep quality and daytime sleepiness on brain structure.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

wget or curl

osfclient

datalad

reporcli

openneuro-cli

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Those methods are design to facilitate data access through HTTP protocol

<https://www.gnu.org/software/wget/manual/wget.html>

<https://osfclient.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

<https://pkg.go.dev/github.com/jimoe/repocli>

<https://docs.openneuro.org/packages/openneuro-cli.html>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

As external dataset, it is out of the scope of EOSC-SIESTA

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Robert Oostenveld (orcid:0000-0002-1974-1293)

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Research Ethics Committee at the Institute of Applied Psychology at the Jagiellonian University and Bioethics Commission at the Polish Military Institute of Aviation Medicine

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.1: Medical Imaging [Input Dataset]

The input dataset contains resting (eyes closed, eyes open) and cognitive (subtraction, music, memory) state EEG recordings with 60 participants during three experimental sessions together with sleep, emotion, mental health, and mind-wandering related measures. The data is described in more detail in an accompanying paper.

The analysis pipeline demonstrated here only uses the tabular data that is included in the dataset. The tabular data contains biometric information, i.e. indirect personal identifiers (age and height). The pipeline should also work with many other BIDS datasets from OpenNeuro.

The data is organized according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. The complete input data consists of 5585 files with a combined size of 30.67GB. The analysis only requires a few of those files to be downloaded.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

In WP15 we provide a number of concrete use cases for secure computing on medical imaging data. We will identify and prepare several representative datasets combined with several analysis pipelines, resulting in specific analysis outputs. The datasets selected for WP15 are all published and open access to allow all project partners to replicate and investigate all details for the use cases. However, the datasets are selected to represent similar EU datasets containing personal data that are the target for SIESTA.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

EOSC-SIESTA WP15 uses neuroimaging data that mainly classifies as primary data. The data has been curated and reformatted, but quality control may be limited and analysis outcomes are not part of the data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data is formatted according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. This relies on domain-specific formats for the individual files, including, but not limited to: JSON, TSV, NIFTI, EDF, BrainVision Core format, EEGLAB, Biosemi, OME-TIFF, ZARR.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The complete input data consists of 5585 files with a combined size of 30.67GB. The analysis only requires a few of those files to be downloaded. The data size is

in the order of a few GB to a few 100 GB. The data can be a single file, but in most use cases is split over hundreds of files.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- Other

We reuse existing data as there is no need to collect new data to demonstrate and identify medical neuroimaging pipelines' computational and interactive aspects. There is enough data available with the required characteristics, both open access and restricted access.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Yulin Wang and Wei Duan and Debo Dong and Lihong Ding and Xu Lei (2022). A test-retest resting and cognitive state EEG dataset. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds004148.v1.0.1

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Other

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/tree/main/usecase-2.1>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://github.com/Bids-standard/bids-schema>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Open Neuro supports API: <https://docs.openneuro.org/api.html>

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

OpenNeuro

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

A test-retest resting and cognitive state EEG dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

wget or curl

osfclient

datalad

reporcli

openneuro-cli

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Those methods are design to facilitate data access through HTTP protocol

<https://www.gnu.org/software/wget/manual/wget.html>

<https://osfclient.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

<https://pkg.go.dev/github.com/jimoe/repocli>

<https://docs.openneuro.org/packages/openneuro-cli.html>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

As external dataset, it is out of the scope of EOSC-SIESTA

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Not applicable

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Variable definitions

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

<https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds004148/versions/1.0.1>

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

Not applicable

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Robert Oostenveld (orcid:0000-0002-1974-1293)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- IRB protocol
- Passwords

For the WP15 implementation, we only use publicly available datasets shared under open-access licenses. For the target datasets that SIESTA is aimed at, which contain sensitive and personal medical neuroimaging data, the following apply: IRB protocols, password protection, encrypted data transfers, and pseudonymisation. Note that anonymisation does not apply, as in that case, the data is no longer sensitive or personal, and SIESTA is not needed as the compute platform.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Other

For the WP15 implementation, we only use publicly available datasets shared under open-access licenses. Unintended data access and data loss are, therefore, not issues (as data is not uniquely stored on the SIESTA platform).

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

For WP15, this is not applicable, as we will not generate new datasets.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

For WP15, this is not applicable, as we will not generate new datasets.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.1: Medical Imaging [Output Dataset]

This dataset corresponds to the output data from a simple example pipeline that analyses univariate tabular data that is organized according to the BIDS standard. The output data consists of the mean of a parameter of interest, such as the age of all participants.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The new dataset is the result of an analysis.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The output data consist of a tsv file with an average of a demographic variable of all participants, such as the age.

The pipeline is only for testing and demonstration purposes, hence we don't anticipate there to be scientific interest in publishing this data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Tab-Separated Values (TSV) file.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1KB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

This implements a typical use case for medical (enduro)imaging data.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

See UC2.1 [Input data] at

<https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/7ba16a18-66ff-47c5-91f9-34b0cbe3c2ff>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The strategy for designing and implementing the pipeline, the requirements for executing the pipeline, and the file formats and size of the output data would be of interest.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

Yes

OpenNeuro

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

https://scicrunch.org/resolver/SCR_001905

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Other

Not applicable

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC4: Text anonymization on sensitive data [Output Data]

In some domains, such as cybersecurity, crime or cybercrime prevention, there is a need to classify unstructured text (e.g., CERT or crime reports) into categories. This classification is prone to be automatized, but the data needed to train the classification models often contain sensitive or private data (e.g. names, locations, IPs, etc.), so such data cannot be disclosed by the interested authorities. Therefore, the models cannot be trained and, consequently, the automatic classification of such reports is not possible. This use case will focus on the anonymization of non-structured text containing sensitive data, with a focus on the subsequent text classification: the anonymized text should be useful to train models that can classify the original (i.e. non-anonymized texts) with an analogous performance as if the model was trained with the original texts.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The data is being re-used. Specifically, it will be gathered from cybersecurity websites, as mentioned in the previous point. Either if we annotate the existing data, or we use it to generate synthetic data, we will take into account all the considerations, ethical aspects, etc.

The new dataset will be subject to a CC license.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The data consists of unstructured text reports, which have not been previously preprocessed (either if we used the original data or generate synthetic data): it will be raw, unstructured text.

However, the dataset is based on data that has been previously published, so it can be considered secondary data, although not subject to a previous cleaning procedure or further preprocessing (apart from the annotations).

1.1.5 What is its format?

All data of the dataset (i.e. the unstructured texts, the annotations and the labels) will be stored in CSV or json format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The dataset should comprise a few thousands of texts with their labels and annotations, so we do not expect more than 5GB of data.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

Other

As it was mentioned above, the objective of the dataset will be: 1) Train a text classification model with the original data to classify the texts, 2) anonymize sensitive data on the original texts, 3) train the text classification model with the anonymized data and 4) assess whether the latter model provides a performance comparable to that of the former.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset has been gathered from websites [1] that have left reports available for research purposes. These reports will be used directly, but can also be used to generate synthetic data in the context of the SIESTA project.

[1] The data has been gathered from websites such as the European Repository of Cyberincidents, Cyberoperations tracker of the Council of Foreign Relations, ICANN cybersecurity incident log, CSIS significant cyberincidents, or the University of Maryland CISSM Cyberattacks database

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Other

This data may be useful in research related to crime prevention or cybersecurity.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

We will register the dataset at the register of the University of León, that will provide a unique hash. We will explore the option of storing the dataset in OpenCAYLE (<https://www.scayle.es/opencayle/>), we expect to get an PID for the dataset there.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Yes, we will provide metadata for the dataset. All the metadata that accompanies every text in the dataset will be described in an accessible format. Currently, we do not follow any particular standard for this, but we are open to follow any guidelines the project requires.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

SensTextRep- XK , being XK the rounded number of samples of the dataset.

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The dataset we would use in the Use Case would be Open, although we may ask to fill a form to control who downloads the dataset.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset can be accessed from the repository where it will be stored, (see answer to question 3.2.1.1), after the completion of a form.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

If there is not an embargo from the funders, the data will be accessible immediately after it will be validated experimentally (see answer to question 1.1.7) and with no temporal restriction afterwards.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The data in the NLP community is commonly shared in csv or json formats.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

We will specify if our dataset builds on another dataset and properly cite them (including their globally unique and persistent identifiers).

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

The data will not be subject to embargo period and will be subject to a CC license. The other research outputs, such as publications, will be made publicly available. The preprint will be made available immediately through, at least, the website of the GVIS research group website and the University of León institutional repository. However, the embargo period for the postprint/published version will depend on the specific journal.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

If we used existing datasets to train/fine-tune a generative model, it would be well documented.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

We use a documented procedure for data entry and annotation. At least 2 annotators label the data and we aim for an inter-annotator agreement that could ensure the quality of the labeling for example by computing the Fleiss's Kappa coefficient or other metric

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Víctor González-Castro (orcid:0000-0001-8742-3775)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Hash functions

The dataset would be protected by blockchain and would have a unique hash identifier. OpenCAYLE (<https://www.scayle.es/opencayle/>) has its own security measures that will safeguard our dataset. OpenCAYLE is part of the European Open Science strategy, in particular with the European Science Cloud (EOSC).

The download of the dataset will be subjected to an internal approval of the petitions by filling a form.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Other

OpenCAYLE is a service of the Supercomputing Centre of Castilla y León (Spain), SCAYLE. Its security policy and security regulations meet the provisions of the Royal Decree 311/2022, which regulates the Spanish National Security Scheme. More details about SCAYLE's security policy can be found on this link: <https://www.scayle.es/ens/>

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

In our Use Case, we will use data corresponding to real cyberincidents which have been made publicly available, and as long as we can amend the GA, it should not be related to Child Sexual Abuse (as it is not being possible to generate a dataset due to lack of textual reports to train a generative model). We will either use them as they are or generate synthetic data by fine-tuning a generative model. In any case, the ethical or legal issues should not be high, as either the data have been disclosed, or would be simulated.

As for the data that would be used in the real scenario, the cybersecurity organization (e.g. CERTs) would own the data, so the data should only be disclosed when and with whom they agree to it, probably after signing an appropriate NDA, and after appropriate anonymization.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Other

The dataset contains sensitive information, but it has either been previously disclosed or it would be simulated.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC1: Epidemiology [Synthetic Populations and Building Information]

The objective of the WP14 is to develop an ecosystem in the SIESTA platform, and by extension in EOSC, able to use data to perform computational epidemic predictions. For this, we will need to build synthetic populations for France, Italy and Spain and to develop models versatile enough for external users to define the particular epidemic process that they want to analyse. What we expect from SIESTA is to have a hosting platform, which can manage the access of users, the environment in which the models can run and the safe sharing of the results with the corresponding user.

The use case objectives are:

To collect data required for epidemiological models (population, mobility, surveillance, etc.) from standard sources public and private.

To develop the tools to share participatory surveillance systems data within the SIESTA framework.

To build the models needed to study propagation scenarios of generic infectious diseases using these data.

To develop a user-friendly interface that will allow the access of expert and non-expert users to the models.

The partners participating in the WP14 are: CSIC (leading), ISI, Inserm, INE and Javier de la Cueva

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The data consulted for this specific use case is primarily intended to be used to generate synthetic populations for input into the corresponding epidemiological models. Most of these data sources are publicly and freely accessible, but they have the restriction that they cannot be stored in third-party data containers for sharing with others. Therefore, these data will not be directly stored on our platform; instead, we will directly store the synthetic populations generated from them. Storing only these synthetic data implies that no personal data is stored, thus avoiding data privacy issues. The main challenge to address is the possibility of de-anonymization in cases where we work with very small population kernels. When generating a population with distributions of characteristics similar to real ones, we could almost exactly replicate the data of the real population for cases with few inhabitants. Therefore, restrictions such as applying minimum population thresholds will be implemented normally by the official statistical offices, which are the source of most of our data.

We have a set of datasets, which we will describe in the following section, that are reused and obtained from third parties. The (initial) datasets are used to generate synthetic populations, which in this case are directly generated by us and are the inputs in our models. Other type of inputs includes population levels

per census tract or municipality and mobility flows between them. The output datasets (called outputs from now on) correspond to the number of cases in each epidemic state per time unit and per geographical area. The geographical areas are defined using the statistical office census tracts divisions, municipalities, and groups of municipalities.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

The data consulted for this specific use case is primarily intended to be used to generate synthetic populations for input into the corresponding epidemiological models. In all cases, we are working with secondary data, which have been cleaned up, analysed, and shared by others. Often, these data come to us in an aggregated form.

Most of these data sources are publicly and freely accessible, but they have the restriction that they cannot be stored in third-party data containers for sharing with others. Therefore, these data will not be directly stored on our platform; instead, we will directly store the synthetic populations generated from them. Storing only these synthetic data implies that no personal data is stored, thus avoiding data privacy issues. The main challenge to address is the possibility of de-anonymization in cases where we work with very small population kernels. When generating a population with distributions of characteristics similar to real ones, we could almost exactly replicate the data of the real population for cases with few inhabitants. Therefore, restrictions such as applying minimum population thresholds need to be implemented.

Among the types of data used, we have the following:

- Places and locations
- Households
- Habits
- Work
- Population

The majority of the collected data comes from the public agencies responsible for the general coordination of statistical services

Sources:

- <https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/>
- <https://www.insee.fr/fr/accuei>
- <https://www.ine.es/>

Places and locations

The data contains cadastral information providing insights into the locations of various types of buildings (residential and other uses), whether they are public (schools, hospitals) or private (restaurants, offices, leisure, among others), as well as statistical data allowing us to determine the number of buildings designated for each type of use, segmented by population centers. It is considered heavy data as it contains information about all buildings nationwide, and the records include geographic information, a field that is heavy and stored in specific formats for this type of data, such as Shapefiles or GeoJSON.

Additionally, these data include information regarding mobility between subregions, which serves to assign destination zones for the population (where they work, engage in other activities) based on their area of origin, which may or may not coincide with their destination zone.

Sources:

- <https://cadastre.data.gouv.fr/>
- <https://www.catastro.minhap.es/webinspire/index.html>
- <https://catastomappe.it/mappa>
- <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

Households

The data contains statistical information about various characteristics of the population, such as the distributions of households by the number of occupants and by the type of family units (with or without children). All this data is presented in the form of estimated absolute numbers and is non-de-anonymizable as it does not contain any personal data. It is stratified by municipality, but data for very small populations are excluded to prevent de-anonymization for small samples.

Habits

The data includes information about the daily movements made by the population in the form of trips classified by destination type (work, home, shopping, etc.), as well as distributions of the time allocated by the population for each of these types of activities.

Work

The public agencies responsible for the general coordination of statistical services in each country provide us with data that allows us to understand how the population is distributed, classifying it according to various variables such as:

Type of occupation (students, employed, retired, unemployed, etc.)

Type of work schedule (full-time, part-time, split-shift, etc.)

Sector where workers are employed

Number of employees by type of institution or job position (education, healthcare personnel, etc.)

Population

We obtain populations divided by characteristics such as municipality or age groups from sources such as the official censuses of each country.

Synthetic population

From the datasets outlined in the previous subsection, we generate a synthetic population for each country to be analyzed. This population is entirely synthetic and does not contain any real personal data. For the agents included in these populations, in addition to assigning them a series of general characteristics such as age, gender, or municipality of origin, which follow a distribution very similar to that found in the real population of each country, we also assign them a series of characteristics that will determine their behaviour once we conduct the simulations. Among these characteristics are:

Origin subregion and destination subregion: in these two areas, the agents will carry out most of their daily activities.

Job position and building where the work is performed.

Household

Number of trips per day and mode of transportation used for these trips

Type of activities carried out during each day (shopping, dining out, leisure activities, visits to medical centers, etc.), as well as the most likely places to be visited of each type based on their regions of origin and destination.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Since data is reused, the formats are diverse depending on the source.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

In the range of Gigabytes

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

As mentioned in previous sections, the inputs used to generate the data included in the platform (synthetic populations) are reused and come from third parties. These third parties, which act as sources of information, are mostly official sources that have already preprocessed their datasets. This approach is suitable because the data is often freely accessible but cannot be stored on third-party platforms. Furthermore, by processing the inputs and then discarding any personal data, we avoid privacy issues related to the data stored on the platform. We are following this procedure because a realistic synthetic population is essential for modelling and simulating scenarios such as epidemiological studies, urban planning, and resource allocation. It ensures that the simulations reflect actual population behaviours and characteristics, which is crucial for the validity and applicability of the outcomes.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The majority of the collected data comes from the public agencies responsible for the general coordination of statistical services

Sources:

<https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/>

<https://www.insee.fr/fr/accueil>

<https://www.ine.es/>

Additionally, this the following list of sources is consulted to obtain information related to places and locations.

<https://cadastre.data.gouv.fr/>

<https://www.catastro.minhap.es/webinspire/index.html>

<https://catastomappe.it/mappa>

<https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

In principle, the outputs obtainable through the offered interface are not intended for commercial use. The target users are individuals involved in research studies related to fields such as medicine and epidemiology. The interface will include prefabricated models (meaning that we will provide some default parametrizations that will represent models of common diseases and which will allow the non-specialized users to experiment) that is more intuitive and tailored to users with less knowledge of computing or epidemiology.

One of the main objectives of the tool is to support the development of studies on various epidemic diseases to understand their behaviour. In addition to its focus on the research community, the tool is also designed for use by institutions that control epidemics to make informed decisions based on the results obtained from simulating different scenarios. The model allows users to adjust parameters such as mobility restrictions or the usage of certain types of buildings. This flexibility in parametrization makes the tool adaptable for a wider range of users.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

https://archive.cdc.gov/www_cdc_gov/csels/dsepd/ss1978/glossary.html

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

DIGITAL.CSIC

The publishable part of the dataset will be stored in an internal repository of the "Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas" (CSIC) called DIGITAL.CSIC.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Appropriate arrangements have been made to deposit the described dataset in an internal repository of the "Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas" (CSIC). This repository, known as DIGITAL.CSIC, is managed and maintained by the institution itself.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Landing page

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The user interface will remain operational beyond the conclusion of the project, ensuring continued accessibility for users. They will be able to

access the simulations and outputs through this interface both during and after the project's completion.

COMMENT: This will depend on the platform developer

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Initially, no specific end date will be set for the platform's operation. Any potential maintenance required after the project's conclusion will need to be determined.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes, metadata will be provided, specifically pertaining to the parameterization of the models and the types of variables used in them. It should be noted that this metadata does not constitute a user manual for the platform, which will be provided separately.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Yes, the metadata includes necessary information regarding the parameterization of the different models that can be launched through the platform, facilitating access to the described dataset/output.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Yes, the metadata will remain available even after the dataset/output is no longer accessible.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

The generated outputs are typical for analyzing the evolution of contagion in diseases and epidemics, like prevalence or incidence among others. The parameters used to define diseases are standard for probability distributions. Parameters such as the definition of disease states will be defined by each user based on their specific case. However, default parameterizations with predefined values for existing and well-known diseases will be provided. These will include commonly used definitions among epidemiologists, defining states such as susceptible, infected, latent, vaccinated, or recovered.

The specific vocabulary used in reference to the language utilized in studies related to epidemics has been selected from the glossary provided by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). The vocabulary can be accessed at the following URL:

https://archive.cdc.gov/www_cdc_gov/csels/dsepd/ss1978/glossary.html

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Yes, a specific nested structure will be defined for all metadata files to facilitate the reproducibility of simulations in the future. This standardized structure ensures that key information related to the simulations, such as parameters, inputs, and outputs, is consistently organized and easily accessible across all datasets. By adhering to a uniform schema, we aim to streamline the replication and comparison of simulations by researchers and practitioners.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The platform is designed to be interoperable and open to external users. However, it's important to note that the outputs of the simulations are not made available to external users.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

We will use the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC BY-NC) license for our dataset/output. The CC BY-NC license allows others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the data for non-commercial purposes, as long as they credit the original creation. This license ensures that while the data can be freely used for educational and research purposes, it cannot be used for commercial gain without permission. By using the CC BY-NC license, we aim to promote academic collaboration and the sharing of knowledge while protecting the dataset from unauthorized commercial use.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

With the downloadable parametrization file (epidemiological models), you can retrieve previous simulations or share your specific model so that it can be simulated by others. This approach ensures both reusability and reproducibility,

allowing for the replication of simulations and the sharing of models for further analysis and validation.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes, the platform is intended to remain operational after the project period concludes. Users will still be able to run simulations and download the corresponding outputs.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

For all data from external sources, we have identified the sources, most of which are official sources from public institutions.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

For synthetic populations, we verify their similarity to real data provided by official sources using statistical methods, like distribution comparison. For data from external sources, the official statistical offices have their own quality control procedures in place.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

- The data included in the platform (synthetic populations) has been completely de-anonymized before inclusion and contains no personal data.
- Regarding the generated outputs, each user, who logs in with their own credentials, can only access the outputs they have generated. Users cannot access the outputs of other users to prevent conflicts of interest.
- user management will rely on user roles and groups. Different roles will be defined (mainly: administrators and basic users). Administrators will have access to the data included on the platform and default users will be able to access only their simulations: the inputs they have used (parametrizations given by default and the ones generated by them) and the generated outputs (at least a certain number of them depending on disk space availability). Outputs generated by other users will remain inaccessible to them.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission

- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

We will ensure that copies of the codes are preserved in internal repositories while the platform is accessible.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

No, there are no ethical or legal issues, as the data is not sensitive from a privacy standpoint. Access to the outputs is restricted to the users who generate them through their own simulations.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC5: Demographics

European governments are moving towards new statistical systems, abandoning costly statistical operations and making greater use of the de-identified administrative data routinely collected by government departments and other agencies. Such data, made accessible for research in ways that prevent the identification of individuals, will provide a robust evidence base to inform research and policy development, implementation and evaluation, while at the same time allowing an in-depth understanding of the rapid sociodemographic changes that are underlying the transformation of European societies. Socio-demographic and health microdata have an important value to researchers from a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines. The access to this information requires the signature of agreements, clearance of users and the use of physical secured rooms. SIESTA will provide a set of tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access and the implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center. This will reduce the burden that statistical offices have on preparing tailored data for individual requests which takes their time from other statistical production, and will allow a wider re-use of statistical and administrative data.

The aim of this WP is to provide a set of tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access. The implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center that can reduce the current situation faced by statistical producers with greater demands by society for information on new issues (such as globalization, welfare indicators beyond GDP, cohabitation, longevity, etc.), greater speed and granularity in the dissemination of data and an increase in quality assurance. This will provide a robust evidence base to inform research and policy development, implementation and evaluation, while at the same time allowing an in-depth understanding of the rapid sociodemographic changes that are underlying the transformation of European societies. Socio-demographic and health microdata have an important value to researchers from a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines.

The user's community will be those interested in Geo-spatial statistical production and analysis, demographers, economists, geographers, health professionals,

governmental and statistical agencies, policy makers and finally, general public via the generation of new statistical and administrative products

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

All the data that will be used within the project has been already generated by Statistical Agencies. The synthetic population data is built on the basis of pre-existing statistical data provided by the Statistical agencies. Primary data is generated in our case by INE and is providing different sets of Data, with different Data access availability. From Census data, publicly available, to very limited access data, Tax returns data, which can only be accessed for previously authorized staff according to the rules of the Tax Authority.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Data come from official surveys and/or from administrative registers. In any case, they are not raw data but data after being processed by a statistics production process.

1.1.5 What is its format?

These data come in numeric form and can be exported to a vast number of digital formats depending on the user's needs. The metadata is associated with the data.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Under 2Gb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

Statistical Offices are entrusted by National Governments to collect, process, preserve data and to disseminate the results. In Spain this is regulated according to the Law 12/1989, of May 9, on the Public Statistical Function.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data is publicly available or accessed under request from the Statistical Offices.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

- Structural

Yes, for Population research you can find FAIR Vocabularies in Population Research

developed by the IUSSP and CODATA co-sponsored a working group to study how population research can benefit from the rapidly developing standards and technologies associated with the FAIR principles. More information here: <https://zenodo.org/records/7818157>

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

TBC

Depending on the level of identification that contains the datasets, repositories of these data sets can be different.

In case that the risk of identification is low (for cross-checking data sets with constraints with not direct identification) data can be freely accessed directly from the INE web site (minimum risk of identification) or can be sent to the researchers premises (medium risk). In this last situation a protocol to authorize the access must be fulfilled.

If the identification is complete or the risk of identification is high (crossing datasets with individual identification in an automatic way) the datasets only can be accessed in secure centers within the INE premises and, also in this case, a protocol to authorize the access must be followed previously.

Datasets from the Tax Agency follow the same patterns, but in this case the sensitivity is higher and in most of the situations they will be treated as the last case previously explained.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

If there is no risk of identification no arrangements is needed.

If the risk is medium, a specific arrangement with the organization that manages the repository is needed. The same holds for all the users that would access datasets with this level of sensitivity.

If the risk of identification in maximum no datasets will be deposited.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

This depends entirely on the type of data. For synthetic data no sensitive information is involved so no special security measures need to be taken.

For original datasets with medium risk of identification, sensitive data may be involved. Physical (physical access control to the premises where the platform is set up and to the rooms where data are stored and where data can be accessed) and logical security measures must be taken (firewall, passwords and other measure to protect data as encryption).

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

If the datasets that will be loaded in the platform of the project are going to be synthetic data without any privacy concerns (generate these kind of data is one of the goals of the project) there is no legal or ethical issues on sharing these synthetic datasets. The only requirement that INE has is to be mentioned as the primary source of information when in all scientific publications based on these data.

If the datasets that will be loaded in the platform of the project are going to be original datasets coming from INE with medium risk level of identification, then legislation about disclosure control of statistical data and personal data protection must be taken into account.

No datasets with identification or with high risk of identification can be loaded in the project platform.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Other

This depends entirely on the type of data. For synthetic data no sensitive information is involved. There is personal information on these datasets but this information is not directly associated with real people.

For original datasets with medium risk of identification, yes, sensitive data may be involved and it contains personal data.

In this last situation (data are sent to the researcher premises): Data controller: As it has been mentioned previously a protocol must be followed to have access to these datasets. The end part of this protocol is a formal agreement between the researcher and INE. This agreement includes the responsibility for the preservation of the security of the datasets to the researcher.

Which GDPR legal basis/grounds are you using for processing it?

Article 3.1 and 21.1 of the R223/2009

Are you implementing data minimisation?

This is a task of the data controller.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.2: Medical Imaging [Output Dataset]

This dataset corresponds to the output data from the MRIQC pipeline for obtaining standard quality control measures from an MRI dataset. The output data consists of quality control measures of each participant, plus group level quality control measures.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The new dataset is the result of an analysis.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The output data consist of number of files with quality control measures.

The pipeline is only for testing and demonstration purposes, hence we don't anticipate there to be scientific interest in publishing this data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

HTML and image files.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

This implements a typical use case for medical (enduro)imaging data.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

See UC2.2 [Input data] at <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/90fc589c-5b07-4efe-8e9b-beb920b8d457>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The strategy for designing and implementing the pipeline, the requirements for executing the pipeline, and the file formats and size of the output data would be of interest.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://mriqc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.3: Medical Imaging [Input Dataset]

The input dataset is a multi-subject, multi-modal neuroimaging dataset that is described in detail in the accompanying data publication. It includes structural and functional MRI, MEG, and EEG data that was recorded during an experimental task on face processing.

The analysis pipeline demonstrated here implements an Event-Related Field (ERF) analysis on magnetoencephalography (MEG) data.

The input data consists of 1671 files with a combined size of 84.82GB and can be downloaded using datalad. The data is organized according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

In WP15 we provide a number of concrete use cases for secure computing on medical imaging data. We will identify and prepare several representative datasets combined with several analysis pipelines, resulting in specific analysis outputs. The datasets selected for WP15 are all published and open access to allow all project partners to replicate and investigate all details for the use cases. However, the datasets are selected to represent similar EU datasets containing personal data that are the target for SIESTA.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

EOSC-SIESTA WP15 uses neuroimaging data that mainly classifies as primary data. The data has been curated and reformatted, but quality control may be limited and analysis outcomes are not part of the data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data is formatted according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. This relies on domain-specific formats for the individual files, including, but not limited to: JSON, TSV, NIFTI, EDF, BrainVision Core format, EEGLAB, Biosemi, OME-TIFF, ZARR.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

84.82GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

We reuse existing data as there is no need to collect new data to demonstrate and identify medical neuroimaging pipelines' computational and interactive aspects. There is enough data available with the required characteristics, both open access and restricted access.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Wakeman, DG and Henson, RN (2024). Multisubject, multimodal face processing. OpenNeuro. [Dataset] doi: doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds000117.v1.0.6

Wakeman, D.G. & Henson, R.N. (2015). A multi-subject, multi-modal human neuroimaging dataset. Sci. Data 2:150001 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2015.1

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Other

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/tree/main/usecase-2.3>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.18112/openneuro.ds000117.v1.0.6>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

BIDS

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The input dataset is already available for third parties

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.4: Medical Imaging [Input Dataset]

The input data is a freely available online resource named "ERP CORE", consisting of optimized paradigms, experiment control scripts, example data from 40 neurotypical adults, data processing pipelines and analysis scripts, and a broad set of results for 7 widely used ERP components: N170, mismatch negativity (MMN), N2pc, N400, P3, lateralized readiness potential (LRP), and error-related negativity (ERN).

The input data consists of about 2000 files with a combined size of 24.1GB. The data is organized according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. Included in this dataset are:

- Raw data files for all 7 ERP components from 40 participants
- The event code schemes for all experiment paradigms
- The task stimuli used for eliciting N170, MMN, and N400, located in the stimuli folder
- Demographic information for all 40 participants ("participants.tsv & participants.json")

The data can be downloaded from ERPCore BIDS dataset or by installing and running the osfclient. The osfclient downloads the data an order of magnitude faster, is more stable for long downloads, and ensures that the directory structure is preserved.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

In WP15 we provide a number of concrete use cases for secure computing on medical imaging data. We will identify and prepare several representative datasets combined with several analysis pipelines, resulting in specific analysis outputs. The datasets selected for WP15 are all published and open access to allow all project partners to replicate and investigate all details for the use cases. However, the datasets are selected to represent similar EU datasets containing personal data that are the target for SIESTA.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

EOSC-SIESTA WP15 uses neuroimaging data that mainly classifies as primary data. The data has been curated and reformatted, but quality control may be limited and analysis outcomes are not part of the data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data is formatted according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) standard. This relies on domain-specific formats for the individual files, including, but not limited to: JSON, TSV, NIFTI, EDF, BrainVision Core format, EEGLAB, Biosemi, OME-TIFF, ZARR.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

24.1GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- Other

We reuse existing data as there is no need to collect new data to demonstrate and identify medical neuroimaging pipelines' computational and interactive aspects. There is enough data available with the required characteristics, both open access and restricted access.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Emily S. Kappenman, Jaclyn L. Farrens, Wendy Zhang, Andrew X. Stewart, Steven J. Luck (2021). ERP CORE: An open resource for human event-related potential research. *NeuroImage*. doi:j.neuroimage.2020.117465

Andrew X Stewart, Emily S. Kappenman, Jaclyn Farrens, Wendy Zhang, Steven J. Luck (2020). ERP-CORE BIDS -Compatible Raw Files [dataset]
<https://osf.io/9f5w7/files/osfstorage>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education

- Other

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/tree/main/usecase-2.4>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

BIDS

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

<https://osf.io/>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.3: Medical Imaging [Output Dataset]

This dataset corresponds to the output data from an Event-Related Field (ERF) analysis on Magnetoencephalography (MEG) data. The data consists of single-subject averages and group-level results.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The new dataset is the result of an analysis.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The output data consist of number of files with ERFs.

The pipeline is only for testing and demonstration purposes, hence we don't anticipate there to be scientific interest in publishing this data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

HDF5 files written by MATLAB, with the extension .mat.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

This implements a typical use case for medical (enduro)imaging data.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

See UC2.3 [Input data] at

<https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/018b3526-a196-4fe3-b34e-10cf5f135b99>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The strategy for designing and implementing the pipeline, the requirements for executing the pipeline, and the file formats and size of the output data would be of interest.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

https://scicrunch.org/scicrunch/resolver/SCR_004849

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

TBD

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UC2.4: Medical Imaging [Output Dataset]

This dataset corresponds to the output data from an Event-Related Potential (ERP) analysis of a number of classical Electroencephalography (EEG) research paradigms. The data consists of 1st level averages and statistical maps, and 2nd level group-level contrasts.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The new dataset is the result of an analysis pipeline.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The output data consist of number of files with ERPs.

The pipeline is only for testing and demonstration purposes, hence we don't anticipate there to be scientific interest in publishing this data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

HDF5 files written by MATLAB, with the extension .mat.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To develop a product

This implements a typical use case for medical (enduro)imaging data.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

See UC2.4 [Input data] at

<https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/033a3b0e-d4aa-4c6d-8c00-b4d7f292dfa1>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The strategy for designing and implementing the pipeline, the requirements for executing the pipeline, and the file formats and size of the output data would be of interest.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

https://scicrunch.org/scicrunch/resolver/SCR_007292

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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